

A Normalized-Enthalpy-Driven Framework for Scaling Laser Powder Bed Fusion of IN738LC: From Single-Track to Bulk Builds

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Abstract

In laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) of IN738LC, achieving consistent melt-pool geometries and defect-free microstructures across single-track and bulk builds remains a critical challenge. This study introduces the dimensionless normalized enthalpy (NE) as a unifying criterion to design and compare process parameters from tracks to multi-layer bulks. First, the powder feedstock was comprehensively characterized, covering morphology, size distribution, rheology, and chemistry, and its effective layer thickness was related to powder relative density. We then fabricated 23 single-track and bulk specimens using combinations of laser power (150–350 W) and scan speeds (0.4–2.2 m/s) chosen to span $NE_{\eta=1}$ values from 11.6 to 18.6. Melt-pool dimensions (width, depth, height), surface roughness (S_a , S_z), porosity (Archimedes, XCT, microscopy) were quantified and correlated with calibrated NE_{η} values (0.57–0.87). We identified a conduction–keyhole transition at $NE = 8.45$, near which surface roughness is minimized and bulk density is maximized. Kendall’s τ_b analysis revealed strong monotonic relationships between NE and melt-pool depth ($\tau = 0.98$), width ($\tau = 0.85$), and porosity reduction ($\tau = -0.72$). Electron backscatter diffraction shifted from $\langle 001 \rangle$ columnar textures at low NE to randomized grain structures at high NE. This study establishes NE as a reliable metric for process parameter optimization and design, enabling tailored performance through precise control of melt-pool properties in LPBF of IN738LC.

Keywords: Normalized enthalpy (NE); Process parameter optimization; Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF); X-ray computed tomography (XCT); Inconel 738LC.

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